

Trace Analysis of Malanjkhanda Copper Ore Samples : A Voltammetric Approach^ψ

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Manuscript received 30 September 1992, revised 3 May 1993, accepted 28 May 1993

Different polarographic methods, viz. DCP, DPP and differential pulse anodic stripping voltammetry (DPASV) have been used for the trace analysis of Malanjkhanda copper ore samples. The results indicate that Cr, Pb, Cd, Zn and Fe are present as traces in the ore. The use of differential complexation of the metal ions present in the sample with NTA has been made for a better separation of polarographic waves/peaks, observed in the analysis. The results have been compared with those observed using AAS. The voltammetric results show the presence of some metal ions in the sample which are not reported by earlier workers.

Atomic absorption spectrometry (AAS), X-ray fluorescence analysis (RFA)¹, atomic emission spectroscopy (AES) and neutron activation analysis (NAA)² have exerted predominance in the trace analysis of metals in natural origin samples. But with the emergence of polarographic and new voltammetric methods, such as normal pulse polarography (NPP), differential pulse polarography (DPP) and differential pulse anodic/cathodic stripping voltammetry (DPASV/DPCSV), scientists are more inclined to use these methods for such analysis³. High accuracy with extraordinary detection sensitivity and ability of oligo determination makes these methods more useful as compared to other methods prevalent in the field.

In continuation of our work regarding the trace analysis of inorganic and organic species in the samples obtained from natural, biological and industrial origin, the authors have undertaken the present work for the trace metal analysis of Malanjkhanda copper ore samples using polarographic/voltammetric methods.

Results and Discussion

In 0.1 M potassium chloride as supporting electrolyte, pH = 3.45 ± 0.02, the DC polarogram

and differential pulse polarogram of the sample solution produce five distinct polarographic waves/peaks (Figs. 1 and 2) with $E_{1/2}$ values of -0.46, -0.59, -0.98, -1.30 and -1.50 V vs

Fig. 1 DC Polarogram of the Malanjkhanda copper ore sample in 0.1 M KCl + 0.005% gelatin, pH = 3.45 ± 0.02; X-axis = 200 mV cm⁻¹, Y-axis = 200 mV cm⁻¹, sensitivity = 10 μA V⁻¹.

SCE, indicating the presence of Pb^{II}, Cd^{II}, Zn^{II}, Fe^{II} and Cr^{VI} respectively. On knowing the presence of the above metal ions in the sample, some synthetic samples having varying concentrations of these metal ions were prepared (Table 1) and polarogram/voltammogram of each sample was recorded under identical experimental conditions. This not only helped in verifying the individual metal ion in the sample but also to study the effect of varying concentration of different metal ions

^ψPaper presented at the Annual Convention of Chemists, 1991.

TABLE I—ANALYSIS OF SYNTHETIC SAMPLES

Sl. no.	Composition of synthetic sample (mg/100 ml)					Amount found using DCP (mg/100 ml)				
	Pb	Cd	Zn	Fe	Cr	Pb	Cd	Zn	Fe	Cr
1.	0.26	0.05	0.06	0.56	0.52	0.20	0.048	0.058	0.052	0.5
2.	0.30	0.05	0.20	0.28	0.52	0.28	0.049	0.02	0.25	0.50
3.	0.26	1.05	0.06	0.56	1.04	0.21	1.02	0.05	0.50	1.00
4.	1.10	1.00	0.12	1.12	1.04	1.05	0.98	0.10	0.14	1.00
	Amount found using DPP (mg/100 ml)*					Amount found using DPASV (mg/100 ml)*				
	Pb	Cd	Zn	Fe	Cr	Pb	Cd	Zn	Fe	Cr
1.	0.25	0.049	0.059	0.055	0.51	0.26	0.06	0.059	0.055	0.515
2.	0.29	0.049	0.19	0.26	0.51	0.30	0.04	0.195	0.275	0.515
3.	0.24	1.04	0.055	0.55	1.02	0.25	1.05	0.059	0.55	1.035
4.	1.08	0.98	0.11	1.09	1.02	1.09	1.00	0.119	1.11	1.039

* Average of six determinations.

Fig. 2. Differential pulse polarogram of the Malanjkhanda copper ore sample in 0.1 M KCl + 0.005% gelatin, pH = 3.45 ± 0.02 ; X-axis = 200 mV cm^{-1} , Y-axis = 200 mV cm^{-1} , sensitivity = $10 \mu\text{A V}^{-1}$.

on the polarographic wave of each other. The results indicated no change in the half-wave potential of the metal ions under study in each of the synthetic sample, confirming the conclusions drawn by the authors regarding the presence of aforesaid metal ions in the copper ore sample. Once the presence of the said metal ions in the sample was ascertained, the quantitative analysis of the sample was done using the method of standard addition.

There was a little problem in verifying the polarographic wave with $E_{1/2} = -0.59 \text{ V}$ vs SCE. This polarographic wave created a confusion as to whether it is due to cadmium or tellurium, because addition of either cadmium or tellurium to the sample solution increased the diffusion current. To overcome this problem advantage of

differential complexation with nitrilotriacetic acid (NTA) was taken into account. On recording the polarogram of NTA-complexed sample solution, this value shifted to more electronegative value with $E_{1/2} = -0.62 \text{ vs SCE}$. Now separate experiments of Cd-NTA and Te-NTA complexes were carried out and the result showed that these complexes produced polarographic waves with $E_{1/2} = -0.62$ and -0.75 V vs SCE respectively; thus confirming the presence of cadmium in the sample.

The analysis for copper was not carried out because the ore being a copper ore had a large percentage of copper and the authors were only interested in the analysis of metals present in traces. Therefore, copper which was present in excess was excluded and the analysis of the trace metal content was carried out by applying the initial potential of -0.2 V SCE. Fig. 3 is a differential pulse anodic stripping voltammogram of the sample.

Minimum detection limits of DCP, DPP and DPASV : Once the qualitative presence of the aforesaid metal ions in the Malanjkhanda copper ore samples were known, their quantitative analysis was done making use of DCP, DPP and DPASV techniques, using the method of standard addition. The minimum detection limits of the techniques for the individual and oligo analysis of the metal ion/ions have been mentioned in Table 2. The

Fig. 1 Differential pulse anodic stripping voltammogram of the Malanjkhanda copper ore sample in 0.1 M KCl + 0.005% gelatin. pH = 3.45 ± 0.02 ; X-axis = 200 mV cm^{-1} , Y-axis = 200 mV cm^{-1} , sensitivity = $10 \mu\text{A V}^{-1}$.

detection limits were examined by preparing synthetic samples. The data (Table 2) show that the DPASV method using a glassy carbon fibre electrode⁴ is highly sensitive in determining the metal ions upto nanogram levels.

Quantitative analysis (DCP, DPP and DPASV) of the sample : The principal use of DCP, DPP and DPASV was for the oligo quantitative analysis of Pb^{II} , Cd^{II} , Zn^{II} , Fe^{II} and Cr^{VI} at pH 3.45 ± 0.02 in the sample. Method of standard

TABLE 2—MINIMUM TRIED DETECTION LIMIT

Sl. no.	Metal ion	Minimum tried detection limit ($\mu\text{g dm}^{-3}$)		
		DCP	DPP	DPASV*
1.	Pb Individual	2.6	0.26	2.6
	Oligo	2.6	0.26	2.6
2.	Cd Individual	1.0	0.06	6.0
	Oligo	1.0	0.06	6.0
3.	Zn Individual	6.4	0.64	12.8
	Oligo	6.4	0.64	12.8
4.	Fe Individual	5.6	0.56	2.8
	Oligo	5.6	0.56	2.8
5.	Cr Individual	5.2	0.052	10.2
	Oligo	5.2	0.052	10.2

* ng dm^{-3} .

addition was employed for the quantitative purpose. The results have been tabulated in Table 3. The precision and percentage recovery of the spiked samples are also been reported. The results indicate that the recovery is over 99.5% for nearly all the metal ions with great precision.

The final analysis results on Malanjkhanda copper ore sample are presented in Table 4. The simplicity of the methods for the qualitative and quantitative

TABLE 3—MALANJKHAND COPPER ORE SAMPLE ANALYSIS*

Metal present = 10^{-2} mg/10 g of the sample

Sl. no.	Metal ion	DCP		DPP		DPASV	
		Added	Found	Added	Found	Added	Found
1.	Pb	—	0.45	—	0.45	—	0.45
		4.10	4.53	4.10	4.54	4.10	4.54
		% Recovery	99.56		99.78		99.78
	S.D.	0.04		0.05		0.05	
2.	Cd	—	0.22	—	0.22	—	0.22
		2.20	2.41	2.20	2.415	2.20	2.415
		% Recovery	99.58		99.79		99.79
	S.D.	0.02		0.02		0.02	
3.	Zn	—	0.35	—	0.35	—	0.35
		1.30	1.64	1.30	1.645	1.30	1.645
		% Recovery	99.39		99.69		99.69
	S.D.	0.01		0.02		0.02	
4.	Fe	—	0.32	—	0.32	—	0.32
		1.10	1.41	1.10	1.418	1.10	1.419
		% Recovery	99.29		99.85		99.92
	S.D.	0.01		0.01		0.01	
5.	Cr	—	0.33	—	0.33	—	0.33
		5.19	5.50	5.19	5.51	5.19	5.51
		% Recovery	99.63		99.81		99.81
	S.D.	0.04		0.06		0.06	

Average of six determinations.

TABLE 4—FINAL ANALYSIS RESULTS OF THE COPPER ORE SAMPLES

Sl no	Metal ion	Amount found (%)	
		Present work voltammetry	By AAS*
1	Pb	0.45	0.45
2	Cd	0.22	Not reported
3	Zn	0.35	0.35
4	Fe	0.32	Not reported
5	Cr	0.33	Not reported

*Ref. 4.

oligo-analysis of the copper ore sample with high dependability, accuracy and precision of determination up to nanogram levels, suggests the utility of the said methods for the analysis of all types of natural origin substances. Besides, the techniques used are less time-consuming and economic as well.

The observed voltammetric results have been compared with these reported earlier using atomic adsorption spectroscopic method⁴ (Table 4). A perusal of the data confirms the utility of the oligo-determining capabilities of the voltammetric methods for such an analysis. In addition, the voltammetric data show the presence of Cd^{II}, Fe^{II} and Cr^{VI} in the sample, which are not reported by the AAS method⁴.

Experimental

Malanjkhand copper ore samples (supplied by the Geology Department, Dr. Harisingh Gour University, Sagar) were collected from the northern flank of the main mine. Centre of the mine was selected for the sampling. The samples were collected from the depth of 60 m.

Polarographic and voltammetric measurement were made on an Elico CL-90 pulse polarograph coupled with IR-108 X-Y polarocard. The electrode system consisted of a dropping mercury electrode (DME) as working electrode, a coiled platinum wire electrode as auxiliary electrode and a saturated calomel electrode (SCE) as reference electrode. The electrochemical cell had a provision for inserting

a bubbler for deaerating the solutions by passing nitrogen gas. A carbon fibre electrode (NF 12, Sigtii Elehtiotatit, U.K.) was used for differential pulse anodic stripping voltammetric analysis (DPASV). The pH measurements were made an Elico LI-120 pH meter.

AnalaR grade chemicals were used. Stock solutions of potassium chloride (2M), Pb^{II}, Cd^{II}, Zn^{II}, Fe^{II} and Cr^{VI} (0.01M) were prepared by dissolving a requisite quantity of their soluble salts in triple-distilled water. Gelatin (0.1%) solution was prepared in hot distilled water. A 0.1 M solution of nitrilotriacetic acid (NTA) (trisodium salt) was prepared. The solutions were standardised by known methods⁵ and diluted as required.

Preparation of sample solution : The Malanjkhand copper ore sample solution was prepared by the sodium peroxide fusion method. Finely pulverised (100 mesh) copper ore sample (10 g) was dried for 1 h and fused with Na₂O₂ (80 g) in a nickel crucible. It was then cooled and the fused mass was dissolved in water (150 ml) and ammonium carbonate (10–15 g) added. The solution was filtered and the insoluble matter was treated with dilute H₂SO₄ (1 : 4). (If a portion remained insoluble it showed incomplete decomposition of the sample). The resulting clear solution was diluted with distilled water (250 ml) and subjected to polarographic/voltammetric analysis.

Preparation of analyte and recording of voltammograms : To copper ore sample solution (10 ml) were added KCl (2 M; 5 ml) as supporting electrolyte and gelatin (0.1%; 5 ml) as maximum suppressor, and the final volume was made up to 100 ml. The pH of the solution was adjusted to 3.45 ± 0.02 using dilute HCl/NaOH solution. The analyte was taken in a polarographic cell equipped with an electrode assembly as described earlier. Pure nitrogen gas was passed through the test solution for 15 min at the beginning of the experiment. The polarograms/voltammograms were then recorded.

On knowing the presence of different metal ions in the sample, synthetic sample solutions

were prepared by taking varying amount of the metal ions (Table 1). The polarograms/voltammograms were recorded and compared with those of the Malanjkhanda copper ore sample.

The method of standard addition was employed in order to evaluate the concentrations of the metal ions present in the sample solution.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to Prof. S. P. Banerjee, Head, Department of Chemistry, and Dean, Faculty of Sciences, Dr. Hari Singh Gour University, for facilities.

References

1. D. M. BANERJEE, M. W. Y. KHAN, N. SHRIVASTAVA and G. C. SAIGAL, *Mineralium Deposita*, 1982, 17, 349.
2. R. G. WEGINWAR and A. N. GARG, "Proceedings of the 28th Annual Convention of Chemists Abstracts", Indian Chemical Society, Calcutta, 1991, p D22.
3. Y. SHEN, *Yankuang Ceshu*, 1988, 7, 122, W. DING and L. WANG, *Yankuang Ceshu*, 1988, 7, 115; L. N. VASIL'VA, I. A. SEMENOV and Z. L. YUSTUS, *Zh Anal Khim.*, 1988, 43, 1244; C. HONGYUAN, F. HUIGUN and G. SHUN, *Yejun Fenxi*, 1987, 7, 25; P. L. MALHERBE, J. W. WAUDBY, and D. K. TOWERS, *Chem S A.*, 1988, 14, 175.
4. R. K. TRIVEDI, Ph. D. Thesis, Dr. H. S. Gour University, 1985.
5. A. I. VOGEL, "A text Book of Quantitative Inorganic Analysis", 4th ed., E.L.B.S., 1978, pp. 324, 482.

